

RUBRICS AS A TOOL FOR FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT IN WRITING CLASSES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Annotation:

The article is devoted to the analysis of the forms and methods of assessment that help improve the quality of learning, namely, formative assessment. Highlighting the role of Rubric as one of the assessment methods that correspond to the listed characteristics and show its effectiveness in foreign language lessons. The use of rubrics is justified for the development of students' self-assessment and mutual assessment skills. Being an active participant in the assessment, the student "immerses" deeper into the material being studied, motivation increases, and faith in success appears.

Keywords: error, utterance comprehension, foreign language, logical connection, score, use of rubrics, use of tools, communicative task, varied vocabulary, formative assessment.

Yozish ko'nikmasini rivojlantirishda Rubrikalarning joriy baholash vositasi sifatida (Ingliz tili darslari misolida)

Annotatsiya

Maqola ta'lim sifatini oshirishga yordam beradigan baholash shakllari va usullarini tahlil qilishga, ya'ni joriy baholash turini ko'rib chiqadi. Rubrikning sanab o'tilgan xususiyatlariga mos keladigan va uning chet tili darslarida samaradorligini ko'rsatadigan baholash usullaridan biri sifatidagi o'rnini ta'kidlab

o'tish lozim. Rubrikalardan foydalanish talabalarning o'z-o'zini baholash va o'zaro baholash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantiradi, vas hu bilan birga baholashning faol ishtirokchisi aylangan o'quvchi o'rganilayotgan materialga chuqurroq kirib boradi, motivatsiya kuchayadi va muvaffaqiyatga bo'lgan ishonchi yanada kuchayadi.

Kalit so'zlar: xato, iborani tushunish, chet tili, mantiqiy bog'lanish, ball, rubrikalardan foydalanish, vositalardan foydalanish, kommunikativ vazifa, turli lug'at, joriy baholash.

Рубрики как инструмент оценивания на письменных занятиях по иностранному языку

Аннотация:

Статья посвящена анализу форм и методов оценивания, способствующих повышению качества обучения, а именно формативному оцениванию. Выделена роль Рубрики как одного из методов оценивания, соответствующих перечисленным характеристикам и показывающих свою эффективность на уроках иностранного языка. Использование рубрик оправдано для развития у учащихся навыков самооценки и взаимной оценки. Будучи активным участником оценивания, студент глубже «погружается» в изучаемый материал, повышается мотивация, появляется вера в успех.

Ключевые слова: ошибка, понимание высказывания, иностранный язык, логическая связь, балл, использование рубрик, использование инструментов, коммуникативное задание, разнообразный словарный запас, форматив оценивание.

Introduction

Modern society puts forward new demands on school graduates. For successful self-realization in any sphere of society, young people need to have high professional and social competencies and be ready to take responsibility for

themselves and others. School education plays an important role in this. The roles of students and teachers are changing. The active nature of learning, individualization and variability make it possible to satisfy the needs of students, placing the student himself at the centre of the educational process. The teacher, in turn, becomes a tutor, a consultant, whose main task is to provide conditions for developing students' abilities and improving the quality of education. In this regard, significant changes are taking place in the assessment system. The student becomes an active participant in the assessment process and uses the results to adjust his educational trajectory. Assessment becomes a mechanism that allows the teacher to improve the teaching process, on the one hand, and motivates students to actively participate in their learning. In this regard, in foreign language lessons, it is necessary to use forms and methods of assessment that help improve the quality of learning, namely, formative assessment. [5] According to M.A.

Pinskaya, formative assessment has the following characteristics:

- student-centered;
- directed by the teacher;
- forms the educational process;
- determined by context;
- continuously;
- rooted in quality teaching. [5]

One of the assessment methods that corresponds to the listed characteristics and shows its effectiveness in foreign language lessons is assessment rubrics. Rubrics are a way of describing assessment criteria that are based on expected learning outcomes and learning achievements. [5] Rubrics help make assessments clear to students: the rubric clearly defines the achievements that are expected. They can be used to assess various forms of speech activity: oral statements, written speech, working with text, assessing a crossword puzzle, etc. In addition, students have the opportunity to participate in discussions about rubrics. Each

rubric has specific criteria and is translated into points.

Rubrics are tables and allow the student and teacher to identify important learning points:

- at what level the student is currently;
- what is missing to achieve an exemplary level;
- what next step needs to be taken to improve the result.

The use of rubrics is justified for the development of students’ self-assessment and mutual assessment skills. Being an active participant in the assessment, the student “immerses” deeper into the material being studied, motivation increases, and faith in success appears.

If we talk about possible problems with this assessment tool, then, in our opinion, this is the description of achievements and the definition of criteria. To avoid controversial situations, they should be as clear as possible and not imply any ambiguity. The second issue that needs to be addressed is the regularity of using rubrics. Like any assessment, rubrics are effective when used systematically and on an ongoing basis.

Below are examples of using rubrics in foreign language lessons.

Example 1.

Crossword Puzzle Score Sheet

Topic: Professions.

Class: 7

Assignment: create a crossword puzzle on the topic “Professions.”

Criterion	High (3 points)	Medium (2 points)	Low (1 point)
Content	Corresponds to the given topic, contains at least 15	Relevant to the topic, contains at least 15	Partially corresponds to the topic, contains

	definitions, the wording is laconic and does not cause difficulties.	definitions, but some of the wording is challenging.	less than 15 definitions, some formulations are difficult.
Literacy in defining terms	The definitions are formulated correctly, 1 mistake is allowed.	There were 2-3 errors in the formulation of definitions.	A significant number of errors were made (4–5).
formatting of speech	It is neatly designed, contains illustrations, and follows all the rules for creating a crossword puzzle.	It is neatly designed; there are some shortcomings in the crossword puzzle.	Designed carelessly, without following the rules for creating a crossword puzzle.

Scale for converting points to marks:

8–9 points – excellent

6–7 points – good

4–5 points – satisfactory

Example 2.

Written work evaluation sheet (photo description)

Topic: Family.

Class: 7

Assignment: describe a family photo.

Criterion	High (3 points)	Medium (2 points)	Low (1 point)
Content	The content is fully consistent	The content partially corresponds	The content partially

	with the given topic (volume of at least 60–80 words)	to the communicative task. The aspects specified in the assignment are not fully disclosed (volume of at least 80–60 words)	corresponds to the communicative task. Not all aspects specified in the assignment are covered (volume less than 80–60 words)
Lexical design of speech	The statement is logical; means of logical communication are used correctly, and a variety of vocabulary and studied speech patterns are used.	The statement is logical; There are some shortcomings when using means of logical communication; a variety of vocabulary and studied speech patterns are used. There may be 2–3 minor errors.	The statement is not always logical; There are numerous errors in the use of logical communication means; 4–5 errors were made.
Grammatical formatting of speech	Various grammatical structures are used; simple and complex sentences are involved, and 1 mistake is allowed.	Several errors were made that do not impede the understanding of the statement; simple sentences are composed grammatically	Uniform grammatical structures are used. Simple sentences contain numerous grammatical errors that do not make the statement

		correctly, and 2-3 errors are made.	difficult to understand.
Spelling of speech	There are no punctuation errors when writing.	When writing, there were 1-2 punctuation errors and several spelling errors that did not affect the understanding of the statement	Numerous spelling and punctuation errors were made when writing, making it difficult to understand the statement.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be emphasized that the method of mutual editing, as an additional method of working on errors, has several advantages, including its communicative orientation and focus on the development of critical thinking. However, like any method of interactive teaching, it requires preliminary preparation of students and careful planning of the lesson. In particular, the teacher needs to introduce students to the criteria for evaluating a specific type of written work, and, if necessary, narrow the editing task to correcting errors of one specific type. When properly developed, the peer editing method effectively complements the teacher’s work in correcting and editing students’ texts, contributing to the development of student autonomy. Thus, assessment rubrics meet the requirements of the modern assessment system, are an effective tool for increasing student motivation, and contribute to the development of self- and mutual-assessment skills.

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